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Handbook for Coordinating and Distributing Snowy Plover Band Combinations in the U. S. West of the Rocky Mountains, Revision 1

Final Report
2023

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2023

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Suggested citation: Stenzel, L. E., M. N. Ashford, C. L. Boser, C. E. Fox, and K. K. Neuman. 2023. Handbook for coordinating and distributing Snowy Plover band combinations in the U. S., west of the Rocky Mountains, Revision 1. Point Blue report to the U. S. Fish and Wildlife Service. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8217911

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This handbook was created to provide guidance to the person(s) charged with coordinating and distributing color band combinations to researchers and monitors of Western Snowy Plovers (hereafter, the coordinator). It is based on the protocols used since 1978, when color bands were first deployed on Snowy Plovers on the West Coast. Because the coordinator may not be a person who has previously banded Snowy Plovers, this handbook contains details and background on issues of consequence to banders that might not be otherwise obvious. The issues include materials (bands and tape durability, availability, ease of distinguishing in the field, etc.), and field challenges and other characteristics of different study sites. Authorization to use color bands on bird species, in general, is obtained through the USGS Bird Banding Laboratory and banding of Western Snowy Plover, in particular, is authorized by the USFWS.

In brief, the job entails:

- Providing banders with left leg color combinations and right leg colors to existing and new projects,
 - Helping the research/monitoring project determine the number of combinations needed, based on realistic funded duration of project and goals (new projects),
 - Knowing the field difficulties/constraints (all projects),
 - Notifying the Bird Banding Laboratory (BBL) which project is using each LLC, so they know who to contact when they receive sighting reports,
 - Determining who should be responsible for answering BBL sighting reports that no project identifies as theirs,
- Keeping track of the current use of right leg colors for left legs that are being relinquished by projects,
 - Request projects that have relinquished left leg colors to periodically provide an update to the FWS of right leg colors that are still on live birds.

INTRODUCTION

Color banding is a powerful method for studying avian movements and demography. Snowy Plovers inhabit open, sparsely-vegetated habitat, thus making it relatively easy to observe color-banded individuals and thereby detect movements or infer survival without recapturing the plovers. Because Snowy Plovers may be highly vagile (Page et al. 1986, Stenzel et al. 1994, Page et al. 1995, Colwell et al. 2007), the obvious purpose of coordinating color banding efforts among programs is to ensure that birds from different projects are distinguishable as they move among sites. Thereby, accurate inferences can be made about plover migration, dispersal, and survival from re-sighting data.

Banded Snowy Plover chick, aqua over blue on the left leg, red over lime on the right leg. Photo by Carleton Eyster.

Researchers and monitors have used color banding to study the Snowy Plover's breeding system and life history, to understand the small- and large-scale movements of breeding and non-breeding plovers, and to measure survival during different life stages (Wilson-Jacobs and Meslow 1984; Warriner et al. 1986; Page et al. 1986, 1995; Stenzel et al. 1994, 2007, 2011; Wilson and Colwell 2010; Colwell et al. 2007, 2013, 2017; Dinsmore et al. 2017). It is most frequently used as an aid to following chicks and determining whether they fledge.

A band combination coordinator, in consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) lead biologists for the Western Snowy Plover, assigns color combinations to new projects that have received permission to use color bands on this species. More frequently, the coordinator follows up, when necessary, with existing banders if there are project changes that require additional combinations. The coordinator also provides combinations for Snowy Plover researchers at western interior U.S. locations whose birds are likely to co-occur with the coastal population of the Western Snowy Plover (the distinct population segment breeding on the Pacific coast) at any time of year. Finally, the coordinator may facilitate communications among the researchers and banders working on Snowy Plovers on the west coast of the U.S. and Baja, Mexico, who have insights and decades of experience with the species, its habitat, and banding techniques to share.

The primary purpose of this handbook revision is to describe the protocols by which band combinations have been assigned to research and monitoring groups with color-banding permission and to update the color-combination-specific information. This report also discusses challenges for observers, banders, and, ultimately, the coordinator, and provides additional practical information helpful for decisions about dispensing band combinations. The state of band combinations reported here will change, as new color-banding projects arise, existing projects conclude, or new combination assignments are made. Authorization to use color bands on bird species, in general, is obtained through the USGS Bird Banding Laboratory and authorization to study and band the federally threatened Western Snowy Plover, in particular, is obtained through the USFWS.

NEW TO THIS REVISION

This revision was prompted by the transfer of color-band assignments from Point Blue Conservation Science to the U. S. Fish and Wildlife Service in March 2023. The task will now be handled by USFWS Western Snowy Plover biologists. Included in this revision are updates (e.g., grey bands – code “e” – are added as an upper band color, OSPR is now included as an entity, and one project is now banding adults with both two- and four-band combinations, right leg colors have been added for a few projects), shown in Tables 1 and 3-5 are updated with changes to assignments and banding practices of projects made since 2020. A discussion of left leg colors that are being relinquished by an existing project for eventual use by another project has been added. And a new appendix (III) has been created to describe and keep track of the details of the transition of left leg combinations between projects. A recommendation for ongoing band combination coordination by more than one person is that a “live” version of Tables 3-5 and Appendix III, be kept on a shared platform. When this handbook is revised, the current version of those tables at that time can be included in the revision.

Table 1: Descriptions and single letter code of the colors used for Snowy Plover color bands.

Color	Description	Code	Band Material	1) Sometimes mistaken for, or fading to, 2) additional notes
Aqua	Light blue	a	Darvic	1) For lime
Blue	Medium blue	b	Darvic	
Green	Medium green	g	Darvic	
Black	Black	k	Darvic	
Lime	Light green	l	Celluloid	1) For aqua 2) plastic bands recently have been unavailable and of uneven quality, tape that adheres well is difficult to find
Grey	Grey	e	Darvic	2) Grey plastic bands added in 2023, in upper position only
Brown	Brown	n	Darvic	1) For yellow, or called dull gold or tan
Orange	Orange	o	Darvic	
Pink	Pink	p	Celluloid	1) Older stock, light pink bands fade to white 2) tape that adheres well is difficult to find
Red	Red	r	Darvic	
Silver	Exposed USGS	s	Metal	2) Designation for metal bands not covered by colored tape
Violet	Purple/violet	v	Celluloid	1) Fades to pink 2) tape that adheres well is difficult to find
White	White	w	Darvic	
Yellow	Yellow	y	Darvic	

COLOR BANDS

There are 13 colors used in color-band combinations for Snowy Plovers breeding in the U. S. west of the Rocky Mountains (Table 1). Bands in ten of the colors are manufactured from durable, ultra-violet ray (UV)-resistant Darvic plastic. Seven colors: aqua, blue, green, orange,

red, white, and yellow, are used by all projects; black, grey, and brown in Darvic plastic, and lime, pink, and violet in celluloid, are used by only some projects. Color bands also may be created from USGS (U.S. Geological Survey, Table 2) metal bands by covering them wholly or in part with all-weather, colored vinyl or plastic tape (hereafter referred to as durable tape), as discussed in Appendix I.

Table 2: A glossary of entity (project or institution) names and their codes.

Code	Entity
BC	Bolsa Chica Ecological Reserve Snowy Plover project
CP	Camp Pendleton region of San Diego County Snowy Plover project
FWS	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
MB	Monterey Bay Snowy Plover project
OD	Oceano Dunes State Vehicle Recreation Area Snowy Plover project
OR	Oregon Snowy Plover project
OSP	Office of Spill Prevention and Response, CDFW for oil spill rehabilitated plovers
PR	Point Reyes National Seashore Snowy Plover project
RU2	Recovery Unit 2 (Del Norte to Mendocino counties) Snowy Plover project
RU3	Recovery Unit 3 (San Francisco Bay area) Snowy Plover project
SBZ	Santa Barbara Zoo (captive rearing facility)
SD	San Diego County Snowy Plover project (a consortium comprising several regions)
SDB	San Diego Bay region of San Diego County Snowy Plover project
USGS	U.S. Geologic Survey
VA	Vandenberg Space Force Base Snowy Plover project
WA	Washington State Snowy Plover project (not banding 2019-2023)

AN OVERVIEW OF BANDING SCHEMES CURRENTLY IN USE

Currently, March 2023, there is one primary banding scheme that is used on both chicks and adults; three projects use two additional banding schemes (Table 2). The primary scheme is a four-band combination using two single-color bands per leg. All projects are assigned four-band combinations. The second banding scheme, used by two projects, is a two-band combination (one band on each lower leg) with a multi-striped band on one leg and a single-colored plastic band on the other leg. A third banding scheme currently being piloted by banders in San Diego County on both chicks (of age > 7 days) and adults, is placement of a USGS band on the left tibiotarsus (upper leg) and a two-character green flag on the right tibiotarsus, with no bands on tarsometatarsi (lower legs, Table 1). Currently, a few plovers are still extant with single bands on the right leg, which were placed on chicks in RU2, Humboldt County, prior to 2020.

Four-band Scheme – This is the most common color-banding scheme. The standard method for the four-band scheme is to place all bands on the tarsometatarsi (lower leg), with the USGS band completely covered in durable tape and placed below a colored plastic band on either tarsometatarsus, and two colored plastic bands on the other leg. Variations on this scheme are 1) the standard method but with the USGS band partially taped so that metal is clearly visible above and/or below the colored durable tape, 2) the use of four plastic bands on the tarsometatarsi, with numbered plastic bands in one or both upper positions, 3) placement of the USGS band on the left tibiotarsus, a colored plastic band on the left tarsometatarsus, and two colored plastic bands on the right tarsometatarsus, 4) the use of either the standard lower leg placement or variation 3 with colored, anodized USGS bands not covered in durable tape. The fourth variation was a method tested but not ultimately recommended by the San Diego Snowy Plover project team, who found the anodized color fading within a couple of years, particularly when placed on lower legs (pers. comm. Travis Wooten). **The left leg colors of four-band combinations are the key to identifying the location at which a plover was banded.** While the number of four-band combinations theoretically available is the fourth power of the number of colors used, some colors or color combinations are not easy to read, bands in some colors are not as durable as others, and, in the past, the availability of bands in some colors ended unexpectedly. **Importantly, restricting the use of some colors on the right leg is advisable to aid in transitioning left leg combinations between projects, when necessary.** Projects' uses of the four-band method are included in Table 3.

Two-band Scheme – This system of color banding is currently used on chicks in two studies. The USGS band is placed on the tarsometatarsus of one leg and a single-colored plastic band on the other. A multi-stripped band is created by covering the USGS band with a durable base tape and applying a narrower tape stripe of a contrasting color around the top or bottom half of the band to create a bi-colored band, or around the center of the band to create a tri-colored band. Projects using the two-band combinations have used many colors from the full palette to create multi-colored bands. Banders in Oregon place the multi-colored band on the left leg, and at Vandenberg Air Force Base on the right leg (Table 1). Often, chicks marked to brood (rather than individually) with the two-band method are recaptured when they recruit into the breeding population, their individual identity determined, and the two-band combinations are replaced with unique four-band combinations. However, recapture is not always possible nor is it always necessary to reband a plover marked with the two-band method in order for it to be individually identifiable. Projects' uses of the two-band method are included in Table 3.

Conventions for Reporting Band Combinations – Band combinations are represented in internal data sets by each project's own protocols but are communicated between projects with the following conventions: Left leg bands are listed before right leg bands and colors on each leg are listed top to bottom. There is a single character code for each color (Table 1). Four-band combinations with all bands on the tarsometatarsi are recorded as either all code letters upper case or all lower case, legs separated by either a space or a colon. Thus wr:ob, WR:OB, wr ob, and WR OB all refer to a plover wearing a white band over a red band on its lower left leg and an orange band over a blue band on its lower right leg. Where there is a band placed on an upper left leg, the color code for the upper leg band is upper case and the band colors on the lower legs are lower case, for example Yl:aw or Yl aw. Methods of indicating

From left to right: Standard four-band method, gn:yy, and variation 1, with variable width tapes on the metal band ny:aw (see Table 1, Four-band Schemes, and Conventions for Reporting Band Combinations for details). Photo credit: Jaimie K. Miller.

From left to right: Four-band method, variation 2, aa:bl and , variation 3, with the upper left band on the tibiotarsus, Yr:ob (see Table 1, Four-band Schemes, and Conventions for Reporting Band Combinations for details). Photo credits: Carleton Eyster and Jacqueline Deely.

From left to right: Two-band method with a bi-colored band, w/g:b, and two-band method with a tri-colored band, g/y/g:r (see Table 1, Two-band Scheme, and Conventions for Reporting Band Combinations for details). Photo credits: Joan Teitler and Steve N. G. Howell.

an unbanded leg or an uncertain combination or band color vary among projects. Most projects use “X” to indicate no band. Monterey Bay uses “U” to indicate no band and “X” to indicate an uncertain combination or color.

A multi-colored band (a USGS band covered with durable base tape and a narrow tape strip in a contrasting color) is denoted with slashes between the colors on the bands. For example, g/y/g:r has a tri-colored metal band on the left, covered with a green base tape and a narrow central yellow tape strip, and a red plastic band on the right; o:y/g has an orange plastic band on the left leg and a bi-colored, yellow over green, taped metal band on the right.

The notation used by San Diego banders for their flagged plovers (see below) is to list the upper leg band color followed by notation indicating a flag and its color (e.g., Fg for a green flag), a period, then the two characters on the flag. For example, S:Fg.BK indicates a silver band on the upper left leg and a green flag on the upper right leg with the characters ‘BK’ on the flag.

A flagged Snowy Plover, O:Fg.BA. (see Table 1, Four-band Schemes, and Conventions for Reporting Band Combinations for details). Photo credit: Catherine Steinberg.

Methods of Efficient Use of Limited Band Combinations – Primary challenges of coordinating and distributing band combinations include deriving enough combinations for the needs of the work being undertaken in each project and advising banders how to make the most of the combinations assigned. Another challenge is that a low rate of band loss should be expected (on <5% of individuals), particularly for plastic color bands. Consequently, limiting the color array used for various projects, considering what combinations might look like with band loss, and limiting the number of very similar combinations may aid in determining the identity of plovers that have lost one or more bands (although site fidelity, characteristic of most Snowy

Plovers, usually aids in tracking individuals even after band loss). Appendix 1 contains more background on the challenges faced by banders or due to bands.

Snowy Plover banders have innovated methods of increasing the number of combinations discernable from those assigned, using various tape widths and positions on USGS bands. These methods create distinguishable variations within single combinations that are apparent in photographs or to project personnel that are aware of subtle difference in taping; they usually are not noticed by naïve observers. For example, when reusing a brood combination within the same year, a strip of the USGS metal band can be left visible above or below the colored tape, or the band may be completely covered with no metal showing, to create three discernable markers. Similarly, with the two-band scheme, the widths of the narrow tapes covering the base tape may differ to create distinguishable variations of the basic combination, but these subtleties may be difficult to create in the field (pers. comm. Dave Lauten). These methods are particularly efficient with combinations when the primary purpose of banding is to determine fledging rates and may be useful when banding to brood (banding all individuals in a brood with the same color combination). The band combination variations are viewable by project personnel at the time chicks are due to fledge, and fledglings are identifiable to year and natal location (or brood) when sighted later by naïve observers.

Table 3. Current banding schemes and leg position of USGS bands. Project codes are explained in the Glossary, page 1. WA and BC projects are not currently color banding. Combination specificity refers to chick combinations.

Project	Combination Specificity ¹	4-band (chicks)	Flags (chicks)	2-band (chicks)	USGS Band (chicks)	USGS Band (adults)
WA	Individual	Y				
OR	Brood			Y	Lower Left	Lower Left
RU2	Brood	Y			Lower Right	Lower Right
RU3	Individual	Y			Lower Left	Lower Left
PR	Individual	Y			Lower Left	Lower Left
MB	Individual	Y			NA	Upper Left
OD	Brood	Y			NA ²	
VA	Either ³	Y		Y	Either ⁴	Variable ⁵
SBZ	Individual	Y				
BC	Individual	Y			Lower Left	
CP ⁶	Individual	Y ⁷	Y ⁷		Upper or Lower Left	Upper or Lower Left
SDB ⁶	Individual	Y ⁷	Y ⁷		Upper or Lower Left	Upper or Lower Left

¹ Combination specificity indicates whether all chicks in a brood receive the same basic combination (Brood) or each chick is given its own combination (Individual).

² Authorized for adult banding but not yet implemented.

³ Chicks previously banded to both brood and individually, but as of 2023 individually.

⁴ USGS bands are placed on left legs for four-band combinations and on right legs for two-band combinations. Both 4-and 2-band combinations used for adults and chicks.

⁵ USGS bands placed on upper left of newly banded adults; in lower position of either leg, or on upper left, on rebanded birds, depending on previous USGS band placement and condition.

⁶ San Diego County personnel may occasionally band chicks on Orange or Los Angeles County beaches. San Diego County methods have been evolving and the table reflects current protocols.

⁷ Chick and adult banding protocols the same.

FOUR-BAND COLOR COMBINATION ASSIGNMENTS

Existing Assignments – Tables 4 and 5 summarize the existing color combination assignments on the Pacific coast, including San Francisco Bay, and also at one interior location, Great Salt Lake. Combinations used by captive rearing facilities are usually derived from the nearest project; one variant method used at Sea World is a bi-colored plastic band on the lower left leg (p/k in 2018-19).

New Assignments – The left leg colors of 4-band combinations (also referred to by some projects as “prefixes”) currently assigned to western U.S. Snowy Plover banding projects use > 80% of the possible current LLCs (Table 4) and the variations on the two-band scheme are already assigned. The possibility of using other markers, such as flags, is still being explored. Thus, prudent use of existing 4-band combinations is still necessary. Because there are few major nesting areas in the Snowy Plover’s Pacific coast range in which banding is not occurring, the number of completely new requests for color-band combinations is likely to be few in the near future. In general, the easiest to read combinations were assigned first. Therefore, re-assignment of left leg combinations that are no longer needed by long-standing projects or projects that have concluded may be preferred over those that have never been used and may not be as easy to read. See the section, below, on transitional and mixed status left leg colors for more information.

For all projects requesting color-banding permission and combinations, answers to the following questions are helpful:

- 1) How does color banding advance the project goals and research questions (in particular, what summaries or analyses are planned)?
 - How much is already known about the questions?
 - How do the questions advance the recovery of the listed Western Snowy Plover population?
- 2) How long is the project expected to last (based on secured funding or institutional support)?
- 3) How many plovers are planned to be color-marked (based on sample sizes necessary and the current size of the target populations to be marked)?

Requesting color-banding permission and combinations provides monitors and researchers an opportunity to consult with permitting agency personnel, the coordinator, and other persons with plover experience on the means of meeting their project goals with minimum band use.

Table 4. Left leg colors (LLC) or “prefixes” of four-band combination assignments. ENT is the banding entity (project) to which they are assigned, see Tables 1 and 2 for codes. The last row includes the upper grey LLCs, newly added in 2023. SPEC indicates an LLC reserved for special use. Asterisk with current entity indicates previously relinquished LLC with some remaining extant plovers by previous entity and *** indicate mixed status LLCs. More information on mixed status and relinquished LLCs in Appendix III. Blanks indicate LLCs available for assignment.

LLC	ENT		LLC	ENT		LLC	ENT		LLC	ENT		LLC	ENT
AA	BC		GA	OD		LA			OA	***		RA	MB
AB	MB		GB	OSP*		LB	OR		OB	MB		RB	MB
AG	MB		GG	OD		LG	SD		OG	MB		RG	OR
AK	RU3		GK	RU3		LK			OK	RU2		RK	RU3
AL			GL	***		LL	SD		OL	SD		RL	OR
AN	VA		GN	VA		LN			ON	RU3		RN	GSL
AO	SD*		GO	MB		LO	***		OO	MB		RO	MB
AP			GP	SD		LP			OP	SD		RP	SD
AR	***		GR	OR		LR	OR		OR	RU2		RR	OD
AV	PR		GV	RU2		LV			OV	RU2		RV	PR*
AW	***		GW	OR		LW	SD		OW	MB		RW	MB
AY	MB		GY	RU2		LY	SD		OY	MB		RY	RU2
BA	MB		KA	RU3		NA	RU3		PA	SBZ		VA	PR
BB	OD		KB	SD		NB	VA		PB	SD		VB	RU2*
BG	MB		KG	SD		NG	RU3		PG	OD		VG	OD
BK	SD		KK	RU3		NK	VA		PK	GSL		VK	GSL
BL	OR		KL	SD		NL			PL			VL	
BN	GSL		KN	VA		NN	RU3		PN	SD		VN	VA
BO	MB		KO	RU3		NO	VA		PO	SD		VO	RU3
BP	SD		KP	SD		NP	SD		PP	SD		VP	
BR	OR		KR	SD		NR	VA		PR	SD		VR	PR*
BV	***		KV	GSL		NV	VA		PV	OD		VV	OD
BW	***		KW	GSL		NW	VA		PW	SD		VW	RU2
BY	MB		KY	GSL		NY	VA		PY	SBZ*		VY	SPEC
EB			EG			EO			ER	WA		EW	
												EY	

Table 5. Right leg colors of four-band combination assignments. Colors used indicated by “Y”; (Y) are those permitted but not yet used. Color codes are in Table 1, page 2, and project codes are in Table 2, page3. WA and BC projects are not currently banding.

Project	Core Colors A B G O R W Y	E	K	L	N	P	V
WA	Y			Y		Y	Y
OR	Y			Y			
RU2	Y		Y				Y
RU3	Y		Y			Y	
PR	Y					Y	Y
MB	Y						Y
OD	Y			Y		Y	Y
VA	Y		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
SBZ	Y			Y		Y	Y
BC	Y						
SD	Y		Y		Y	Y	

Estimating fledging success is the most common reason color banding is requested; therefore, as an example, this project goal is discussed in more detail here. Some research or monitoring goals can be met without color banding. For example, for a moderate- to large-sized study area with a small-sized population of plovers, determining fledging of chicks may be achieved by monitoring broods (or broody parents) through the 28-day chick-rearing period, with an emphasis of effort from the chick age of about 26 days onward (e. g., Ruhlen et al. 2003). A benefit of not capturing and handling adults or chicks is that the plovers may be less wary of researchers and permit close approaches and view of broods that they might not allow after capture and banding. On the other hand, in expansive study areas in which it is difficult to track broods (e. g., salt evaporation ponds, broad alkali lake shores), it may not be possible to estimate fledging success without banding chicks. Considerable tracking effort is needed at the time a brood is due to fledge, when all chicks of a brood usually are still with attending parents. Banding all chicks of a brood with the same combination (banding to brood) is usually sufficient for meeting the goal of estimating fledging success. The requesting project should carefully assess the sample size of marked plovers required for their project objectives. Sources such as Henkel et al. (2020) may provide useful guidance.

The project duration is important for several reasons. Adult Snowy Plovers have an expected life-span of ~3 years, commonly live to 5 years, and in rare cases may live to 15 years or more (Paton 1994, Page et al. 2009, Colwell 2017). Therefore, banded plovers may outlive the studies in which they are marked. If a project ends and there is no further tracking of the birds that have been banded, the combinations used may be “in limbo” for many years unless their tracking is taken on by another project. Some project goals advanced by color-banding may not be possible with short-term studies. For example, three years is the shortest study duration useful for standard mark-recapture analytic methods to estimate annual survival.

When a bander receives a set of combinations and begins to use them, the combinations will eventually sort into three categories:

- 1) Available – combinations that have not been used, or have been used in the past but for which there is evidence that there are no longer live plovers wearing the combination (such as discovery of a banded carcass or no credible sightings for at least three years)
- 2) In Use – combinations on one or more plovers (from a year cohort) known or believed to be alive
- 3) In Limbo – combinations on plovers that may still be alive, but have not been seen recently, so it is not yet certain the combination can be recycled to become “Available”

Transitional and Mixed Status Left Leg Colors – In some situations left leg color may not be assigned to a single entity. Transitional left leg colors are those that have been previously used by a project but are released for partial use to a successor project. Partial use by the successor project is required because some individuals from the previous project with those left legs are still alive, so some of the right leg colors are not currently available. Mixed status left leg color are deliberately created by reserving one or more left leg combinations for requests involving only a few combinations. For example, for a small number of broods captive-reared by an entity that functioned only in 2020, the left leg vy was assigned with right leg colors limited to green, violet, and yellow, yielding 9 combinations to band the chicks that fledged.

Transitional left leg colors have been created in recent years by the conclusion of Snowy Plover banding and close monitoring in Washington State in 2018 and by the release of some left leg colors for which there are few plovers currently alive by the Monterey Bay project. Without complete knowledge of which Washington plovers were still extant, one of their left legs was assigned to RU2 biologists who used variation 1 of the standard four-band scheme to differentiate their plovers from any WA plovers with the same combinations still alive. In the case of Monterey Bay left leg releases, color-banded plovers are still closely monitored. Thus, right leg colors on plovers still alive can be held back initially and other right legs released for use by a successor project. As the death of Monterey Bay individuals with released left leg color is determined, their right leg color become available to the successor project and, eventually, all right legs combinations will be cleared for use. Release of left leg colors by the Monterey Bay project has happened numerous times in the past, particularly during the 1990s when many new banding projects on the West Coast were launched. The benefit of transitioning left leg color between projects is that the currently used combinations are often highly desirable (easily read, color bands available in Darvic, good tape availability). The downside is that determining where individuals are from often requires researching records from two projects. In general, transitional left leg colors should be a second choice if a desirable left leg combination is available, unencumbered by prior use issues.

EXPECTATIONS

Both the coordinator and the participating bander should agree to the following actions:

The coordinator:

- 1) Provide sufficient combinations so that each combination is at least unique to year for the site, until the combination can be recycled.
- 2) Provide contact information for other projects that are color banding Snowy Plovers on the Pacific coast, and guidance on the use of the Snowy Plover Google groups for exchanging sighting data (snpl_bandreporting@googlegroups.com).
- 3) Request access for the new bander to the Snowy Plover Google group from the group manager, currently Amber Clark (Amber.Clark@parks.ca.gov).
- 4) Facilitate communication between projects when a plover is mis-banded with another project's left leg combination. (Banding errors of this sort happen occasionally, and they need to be reported to avoid misinterpretation of sightings. If the project assigned the left leg combination holds the combination in their Available list, it can be moved to In Use; if the combination is In Use or In Limbo, there may be ambiguity about the source of a plover when that combination is sighted.)
- 5) Provide Appendix 1 of this report, which contains useful information from decades of experience, collected from personnel of nine existing Snowy Plover projects.

The bander:

- 1) Use best banding practices to minimize band loss and/or injury to banded plovers.
- 2) Keep track of the three types of combinations, Available, In Use, and In Limbo, by maintaining sighting records of their marked birds. This allows banders to reuse their combinations when the birds wearing them have perished.
- 3) Notify the coordinator if they mis-band a plover with a left leg combination they were not assigned.
- 4) Agree, when their project concludes, to assist the coordinator and other banders by passing on banding records to the FWS Snowy Plover lead and to the coordinator, annotated to indicate which combinations are Available and, for those In Use or In Limbo, the number of individual plovers (if banding to brood). Ideally, a neighboring project could take over tracking the sightings of the plovers that are still being sighted.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Years of experience and collaboration between James Watkins of the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and Gary Page and Jane Warriner of Point Blue Conservation Science established the core protocols on which this handbook is based. Banders, listed on the title page, from nine West Coast projects studying Western Snowy Plovers generously provided information, insights, and wisdom from their years of experience, and feedback on various drafts of this handbook. Their careful special efforts to innovate marking techniques for this species have been invaluable. The Handbook has greatly benefited from their contributions. Catherine Hickey of Point Blue Conservation Science made many helpful suggestions to an earlier draft of

this handbook. Esther Haile's skills were indispensable in the final report production. This is Contribution 2452 of Point Blue Conservation Science.

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APPENDIX I: Color Banding Western Snowy Plovers – Wisdom from the Experiences of Existing Project Personnel

Best practices for color banding Snowy Plovers are suggested here based on the experiences of personnel from projects that have banded thousands of plovers and, therefore, have had the opportunity to observe many plovers closely after banding, note problems that might arise even uncommonly, and develop methods to minimize problems. The following is meant to highlight facts and issues that a person coordinating and distributing band combinations should be aware of and **is not meant to be a comprehensive training guide for banding Snowy Plovers.**

Minimizing injuries to plovers' legs and feet, and band loss are two important aims of best banding practices. Injuries to the feet or legs of *unbanded* Snowy Plovers occur fairly rarely on the Pacific coast and may be due to a variety of hazards in their environment (pers. comm. K. Castelein, C. Eyster, D. George, D. Lauten, K. Neuman, G. Page, and author's observations). Examples include entanglement in thin kelp strands or human debris such as fishing line or kite string that is discarded in the plover's habitat, or natural and contaminant substances that adhere to feet. Human hair and other fibers have been found wrapped around plover feet and legs, cutting off blood circulation to toes (pers. comm. Douglas George). Because bands may make plovers more vulnerable to hazards in the environment, and bands may pose problems as they deteriorate with age or if they are poorly applied, it is important that banders employ steps to minimize risks. Band loss is another concern, particularly for plastic color bands. Band loss is usually preceded by the opening of the split band, which also may injure the plover's leg or foot (pers. comm. C. Eyster, D. Lauten).

USGS bands for plovers are a special size, 1P, between 1A and 1B. If tape is to be applied to USGS bands, cleaning of the bands to remove all oils, either from manufacture, contamination, or handling, is highly recommended. Tape is more likely to come off USGS bands if there is any oil residue, including that which may accumulate on a string of partially used bands subject to regular handling.

Split-ring color bands, the style used for Snowy Plovers, may fall off the leg or may pinch and injure a plover's leg or foot if the band opens at the split. The wrap-around style of plastic band is not advised because of the danger of substrate particles packing between the band layers, causing the band to pinch the leg. Steps to avoid the problems of band loss and injury start with maintaining banding equipment in the best condition possible, including keeping bands clean and stored in a cool environment, and culled if they have defects or become deformed.

To ensure plastic bands stay securely closed their split ends should be lightly heat-soldered together after application, the bands wrapped with durable tape in a color matching the band, and the tape's ends lightly melted down to avoid its unraveling. The tapes that have proven to be the most durable are 3M[®] vinyl auto pin striping tape (spooled in 1/8-, 3/16-, and 1/4-inch widths) and Avery[®] 900 Ultimate Cast Opaque vinyl tape (sheets). USGS bands are ¼ inch tall and can be covered in spooled tape of that width. Plastic bands are 3/16 inch tall. Multi-colored bands or USGS bands not completely covering the metal can use tapes of 1/8 or 3/16-inch widths.

The quality and availability of color bands and durable tape may pose a challenge for banders. The shade of some colors available from a manufacturer may change over time and color may differ among manufacturers. Plastic bands should be the highest quality available, currently split plastic rings with a 3.1mm inside diameter. Most colors currently are available in UV-resistant Darvic plastic, but some are available only in celluloid, which is both prone to fading and also less durable than Darvic.

An additional banding caution to note is the occasional chick that hatches without its legs and feet having reached a size at which they will retain bands. If there is any indication that a band is slipping over the chick's foot, bands should be removed and banding abandoned for that individual.

With over ten projects using color bands on Snowy Plovers in the western U. S., combinations that are relatively easy to read in the field are limited in number and it is important that assigned combinations are reused when there is sufficient evidence that the plovers they were placed on are no longer alive. Therefore, it is important that record-keeping by banders is adequate to monitor subsequent sightings of marked birds and determine when a combination may be reused. While birds that have established a two or more year pattern in their use of beaches or other habitat very rarely change that pattern, young or newly-marked adult plovers commonly disperse from their banding location. For the latter groups, which may be harder to track at their new locations, it takes several years to determine that individuals have perished, and combinations may be reused. At Monterey Bay, a two- to three-year absence, determined by a lack of credible sightings, is required before recycling combinations, if there is no other strong, supporting evidence that an individual is no longer alive.

APPENDIX II: The History of Snowy Plover Band Combination Coordination

In the mid-1970s, when the first studies using color bands on Snowy Plovers in the western U. S. were commenced, the Bird Banding Laboratory (BBL) in Patuxent, MD tasked the first permitted applicant for color band use on a species with the coordination of combinations for subsequent applicants. The BBL also sent (and sends) the first permitted project all color-banded plover reports they receive, with the expectation that these reports will be distributed to the appropriate project. Thereby, (Point Reyes Bird Observatory, DBA) Point Blue Conservation Science has coordinated color band combinations and fielded BBL sighting reports west of the Rocky Mountains since 1978. Gary Page, in consultation with Jane Warriner, was the individual coordinating band combinations and Frances Bidstrup responded to BBL sighting reports until 2015-2016, when these jobs transitioned to the first author of this handbook. Since the 1993 listing of the Pacific coast population segment of Snowy Plovers as Threatened under the Endangered Species Act, that coordination has been done in consultation with the Snowy Plover lead biologist, from the Arcata Field Office. Since the early 1990s, the number of groups studying and color banding Snowy Plovers in the western U. S. has grown from no more than three at any time to over ten. The current distribution of band combinations is the result of a 40-year history of requests from numerous monitoring and research groups. In March 2023, the coordination of band combinations transitioned to the Fish and Wildlife Service.

APPENDIX III: Mixed Status Left Leg Combinations

Some left leg combinations (LLC) are not currently assigned to a single entity because they 1) have been relinquished by one project, with some number of plovers still alive with that left leg or 2) are in use by more than one project by design. The following table is meant as an aid to keeping track of these mixed status LLCs. In the Status column, “Relinquished by” indicates the previous user of the combination; “Assigned to” indicates assignment to subsequent or multiple entities if they have been made.

LLC	STATUS	RIGHT LEG COMBINATIONS AND OTHER NOTES
AO	Relinquished by MB	MB: yv extant 3/2023 (original transfer made ~ 2016)
AO	Assigned to SD	San Diego, With all regular SD RLC (right leg colors)
AR	Relinquished by MB	MB: ab, bo, go, l, rw, ry, yo, (ar, aw, ob) extant 3/2023
AR	Assigned to	(Might include K, N, P, or V for first 2 years)
AW	Relinquished by MB	MB: ba, br, gp, ll, og, wo, wr,yo, (ow) extant 3/2023
AW	Assigned to	(To include K, N, or V for first 2 years)
BV	Relinquished by WA	WA: none believed to be extant 3/2023, WA to update after 2023 monitoring
BV	Assigned to	
BW	Relinquished by MB	MB: ag, ar, oo,ro, yo,yw, (bb, or) extant 3/2023
BW	Assigned to	(Might include K, N, P, or V for first 2 years)
GB	Relinquished by MB	MB: gw, oo, oy extant 3/2023
GB	Assigned to Huntington OS	Used: ak, bk, kk, rk, wk, wy, ka, ky (used by VSFB: kb, kr, kw)
GB	Assigned to OSPR	Proposed: aa, ab, ag, ao, ar, aw, ay, ba, ga, oa, ra, wa, ya, bb, bg, bo, br, bw, by, gb, ob, rb, wb, yb, rg, ro, rr, rw, ry, gr, or, wr, yr In reserve: an, bn, nn, rn, wn, yn, na, nb, nr, nw, ny
GL	Relinquished by MB	MB: yl extant 3/2023 (gw, wy 2020)
GL	Assigned to	
LO	Relinquished by MB	MB: gg, ro extant 3/2023
LO	Assigned to	(Might include K, N, P, or V for first 2 years)
OA	Relinquished by MB	MB: ag, bb, br, bw, ga, og, wl, ya, yr, yy, (aa, bb, ow, rr, oa) extant 3/2023
OA	Assigned to	(Could require including K, N, P, or V for first 2 years – none of these colors on Monterey Bay right leg for OA)
PY	Relinquished by MB	MB: vr extant 3/2023
PY	Assigned to SBZ	Using same RLC as OD
RV	Relinquished by WA	WA: possibly extant 3/2023, WA team will update after 2023 monitoring
RV	Assigned to	PR
VB	Relinquished by WA	WA: none believed to be extant 3/2023, WA team will update after 2023 monitoring

